

EFFECT OF ADDED DEFATTED BENISEED ON THE QUALITY OF ACHA BASED BISCUITS

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ABSTRACT

The acha (*Digitaria exile staff*) grain was washed (tap water), sun dried, milled and sieved (400µm sieve aperture) to produce acha flour. The beniseed (*Sesamum indicum*) seeds were sorted, washed, sun dried, milled, defatted (using ethanol), dried and sieved (400µm sieve aperture) to produce beniseed flour. The defatted beniseed flour was substituted into the acha flour at 0-20% to produce beniseed-acha composite flour. This was mixed with fat, sugar, salt, baking powder to produce batter. The batter was rolled (on a steel table), cut into shapes (using biscuit cutter), placed on greased trays and baked at 160°C for 20 minutes. The effect of added defatted beniseed on the physical, chemical and sensory quality of acha-beniseed composite biscuit were evaluated. The protein, fat, moisture, ash, breaking strength and spread ratio increased from 10.5 to 12.9, 1.80 to 2.15, 1.0 to 1.6, 1.20 to 3.20%, 1.49 to 1.67kg and 6.0 to 7.25, respectively with increase in the percentage of added defatted beniseed. However, the average means of the sensory properties decreased from 8.30 to 4.30, 7.20 to 5.80, 8.50 to 6.30, 8.30 to 4.20, and 7.90 to 3.70 for color, texture, appearance, flavor and general acceptability, respectively at $p \leq 0.05$ level of acceptance. The addition of defatted beniseed above 10% has a significant negative effect on the acceptances of the product. There was an increase of 12 and 16.4% of protein and fat content respectively, at the maximum acceptance level (10%) of the added beniseed flour.

KEYWORDS: Effect, Defatted Beniseed, Quality, Acha Biscuits

INTRODUCTION

The nutritional value of biscuits varies with the type of cereal used. Biscuit is known to generally contain fat (18.5%), carbohydrate (78.23%), ash (1.0%), and protein (7.1%) and salt (0.85%) (Okeagu, 2001). The dependence on the use of wheat flour is one major constraint in biscuit production. The high demand of wheat flour and the inability of the country to meet this demand calls for research into alternative local sources of flour baking example cassava, *acha*, millet, sorghum, etc.

Nigeria is finding itself more and more caught up in “wheat trap” in which most of its foods are made from wheat a foreign cereal. (Whitey, 1971). Most of the common local cereal grains including *acha*, though having similar structure and composition were left in a state of under development and inadequate processing. Due to lack of attention, *acha* is still ergonomically primitive because of its very tiny seeds size resulting in difficulty in dehulling.

Today, plant proteins play significant roles in human nutrition, particularly in developing countries where average protein intake is less than the required. Due to inadequate supplies of animal proteins, there has been a constant search for new protein sources, for use as both functional food ingredients and nutritional supplements, (Obizoba, *et al.*, 1994). Plant protein products are gaining increased interest as ingredients in food systems throughout many parts of the world. The final success of utilizing plant proteins as additives depends greatly upon the favorable characteristics that they impart on foods. Beniseed flour contains substantial quantity of tryptophan and methionine, an important essential amino acids needed for the

healthy living (Eleazar *et al.*, 2003). The development of defatted beniseed flour would provide industry with new high protein food ingredients for products formulation and protein fortification (Uwala, 2002).

Acha has been researched in several areas (Bolaji *et al.*, 1993; Funanbial, 1998; Irving and Jideani, 1997; Jideani and Akingbala, 1993; Jideani *et al.*, 1994; Lasekan 1998; Ayo and Nkama, 2003; Ayo and Nkama, 2004; Ayo and Nkama, 2006; Ayo *et al.*, 2008a; Ayo *et al.*, 2008b; Ayo *et al.*, 2007a; Ayo *et al.*, 2007b).

The relatively low quantity of *acha* protein has called for supplementation particularly with inexpensive stable pulse and legumes such as soybean. Research has shown that nutrients composition or proximate composition of food is not enough to determine nutrient bio-availability (Davies and Austine 1982) hence the use of animal feed. The biological utilization of a protein is primarily dependent on its digestibility (Hooda and Jood, 2005).

Acha, contains high water absorption capacity that gives it capacity to be utilized in baked foods. It also contain pentosans(Lasekan and Lasekan 1998, Ayo 1998) which gives it the ability to form gel in the presence of oxidizing agents at room temperature with high residual protein coupled with high levels of sulphur and hydrophobic amino acid residues which makes it useful in baking (Obizoba et al, 1994). The recent finding of the unique property of *acha* flour in relatively lowering the blood glucose level (Ayo *et al.*, 2007) and the subsequent reducing the diabetic populace has made the same an attractive research focus in the recent times.

This work is aimed at improving the nutrient intake of populace particularly the diabetics, by supplementing the underutilized benniseed grains into *acha* flour to produce *acha*-beniseed composite biscuits.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The *acha* and beniseed grains were purchased from the Bauchi Central Market. The *acha* grain was dried (APV Cabinet Drier, 45°C), milled (Attrition Mill Yamaha Japan), and sieved (350nm aperture) to produce *acha* flour. The beniseed grains was sorted, washed, dried (APV Cabinet Drier, 45°C), milled and defatted using ethanol and dried (APV Cabinet Drier, 45°C), and sieved (350nm aperture) to produce benniseed flour. The defatted beniseed was supplemented (at 0.5, 10, 15, and 20%) into the *acha* flour to produce composite flour. Fat and sugar was fluffed into sucrose sugar and added to different proportion of composite flour added and mixed with condiments (salt, baking powder, egg and milk) to form batter. The batter was rolled (on a steel table), cut into shape (using biscuit cutter), placed on greased trays and baked at 160°C for 20 minutes.

Physical Analysis

The Spread Ratio was determined by measuring the length and height of three rows and column, respectively of five well formed biscuits. The spread ratio is calculated as diameter divided by height (Gomez *et al.*, 1997).

The breaking strength was determined by adapting Okaka and Isieh's (1997) method. Biscuit of known thickness (0.4cm) was placed centrally between two parallel metal bars (3 cm apart). Weights were added on the biscuit until the biscuit snapped. The least weight that caused the breaking of the biscuit was regarded as the break strength of the biscuit.

Chemical Analysis

The protein, fat, ash and moisture content of the samples were determined. The carbohydrate content was obtained by difference of values above from hundred (AOAC, 1990).

Sensory Evaluation of beneseed-acha composite biscuits

The sensory evaluation of the samples was carried out for consumer acceptance and preference using 20judges (students from Department of Food Science and Technology and students from Department of

Mechanical Engineering of Federal Polytechnic, Bauchi), randomly selected using a Nine point Hedonic scale (1 and 9 representing “extremely dislike” and “extremely like”, respectively). The mean scores were differentiated using Analysis of Variance Methods. The qualities assessed include colour, texture, taste, flavour and general acceptance. Coded samples of the same size and temperature (29°C) were served on a coloured (white) plate of the same size to judges in each panel cupboard under the florescent light. Only one sensory attribute was tasted at one sitting.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of added defatted beniseed flour on physiochemical quality of *acha* – beniseed composite biscuit.

The effect of added beniseed flour on the physiochemical quality of *acha* based biscuit is summarized on Table 1.

The moisture content of the *acha*–beniseed biscuit increased from 1.0 to 1.6% with the increase in the defatted beniseed flour concentrate (0-20%). This could be due to the increase in protein content. Proteins particularly from cereals have been noted to have high affinity for moisture and will always absorb the same if available (Jideani and Akingbade 1993; Alabo 2006)

The protein content increased from 10.5 to 12.9% with increase in the percentage (0-20) addition of defatted beniseed flour. This could be due to the addition of the defatted beniseed, a legumes which are noted to be a good source of protein (Olayanju *et al.*, 2006; Eneche, 2005). They contain powerful antioxidants called lignin which are also anti-carcinogenic and contain phytosterols which block cholesterol production. Their protein has a good balance of amino acids with a chemical score of 62%, and a net protein utilization of 54% (Alabo, 2007). These characteristics give sesame the potential of being a source of protein supplementation in cereal based foods.

The fat content increased from 1.8 to 2.15% with increase in the percentage (0 – 20%) of defatted beniseed flour. The increase was not significant due to the defatting of the added beniseed. Similar non significant increase has been noted in the use of defatted legumes such as pigeon, and groundnut (Olayanju *et al.*, 2006; Ayo, 2003).

The ash content increased from 1.2 to 3.2% with increase in the percentage (0 – 20%) of defatted beniseed flour. The increase in the ash content could make the product a good source of minerals as observed in similar works (De Lemen *et al.*, 2003; Addo, 2005). The seeds are rich in manganese, copper and calcium (90mg per table spoon for unhulled seeds, 10mg for hulled seeds and contain vitamin B, (thiamine and vitamin E (tocophenol) (Sosanya, 2007).

The carbohydrate content decreased from 35.59 to 80.15%.as the percentage of defatted beniseed flour increased (0 – 20%). The decrease could be due to the low carbohydrate content of the added defatted beniseed flour as has been observed in similar research works using legumes (Kent 1984; Ayo 1998).

Effect on the Physical quality

The effect of added beniseed flour on the breaking strength of *acha*–beniseed biscuit increased from 1.49 to 1.67kg with increase in defatted beniseed flour concentrate(0 – 20%). This could be due to low quantity of carbohydrate content and poor quality of protein in term of functionality in beniseed and *acha* flour which has been observed to be the important factors in the formation of bonds that determine the strength of food (Fennema 1995).

The spread ratio of *acha*–beniseed biscuit increased from 6.0 to 7.25 with added defatted benniseed flour. The increase in spread ratio is an indication of poor cohesions of the net work of the protein and carbohydrates which are the principal nutrients in the product (Gomez *et al*, 1997; Ayo and Nkama, 2003). The poor cohesion could allow the outflow of some ingredients such as sugar that could melt at the high temperature of baking hence increasing the spreadibility of the material.

Effect of added defatted beniseed flour on the sensory quality of acha based biscuit.

The addition of defatted beniseed flour decreased the mean score of colour and texture from 8.30 to 4.30 and 7.20 to 5.80, respectively with increased percentages (0 – 20%) flour of beniseed as shown in Table 2. The decrease in the mean score of the texture could be due to the same reason adduced to that of break strength.

The addition of defatted beniseed flour increased the mean score of flavor from 4.20 to 8.30 with increase in the percentage (0-20%) of added defatted beniseed flour. This could be due to the possible by products flavor (fufury, amyl compounds) of protein in the beniseed and the *acha* carbohydrate which is acceptable in most baked products like biscuits (Fennema, 1985). However, the addition of defatted beniseed flour decreased the mean core of taste from 7.70 to 3.70 with increase in the percentages (0 – 20%) of defatted beniseed flour. This could be due to the bitter taste of some inherent compounds in beniseed flour particular at high temperature (Iwe, 2000).

The addition of defatted beniseed flour decreased the acceptability of the product on mean score that ranges from 7.90 to 3.70. The addition of defatted beniseed flour is acceptable up to 10% fortification with beniseed flour in *acha* – beniseed composite biscuit with a corresponding 11.9% protein.

CONCLUSION

The addition of defatted beniseed flour in the production of beniseed-acha composite biscuits has been found to be acceptable up to 10% which has a corresponding 125% (10.5-11.90%) and 16.3% (1.80-2.10%) of protein and fat respectively.

The economic impact of using beniseed-acha composite flour in manufacture of biscuits lies in the reduced need for wheat for wheat being imported. In developing countries like Nigeria, where there is ban on wheat importation, utilization of *acha* and beniseed for biscuit production should be encouraged as the biscuits are a good source of protein and energy. Biscuit consumption is high in Nigeria; therefore, *acha*-beniseed biscuits will serve as vehicle for increasing intake of protein and calories in Nigerian diets. The production and acceptability of *acha*-beniseed composite biscuits will to a great extent provide variety of food for the diabetics as recent findings has recommended *acha* for such populace

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Table1: Physiochemical Quality of Acha Beneseed Composite Biscuit

Sample parameters		Moisture %	Ash %	Protein %	Fat %	Carbohydrate %	Break strength kg	Spread ratio	Calorific (kca) intake
Acha%	Beniseed%								
100	0	1.00	1.20	10.5	1.80	85.50	1.49	6.00	400.2
95	5	1.20	1.80	11.3	1.90	83.80	1.54	6.33	397.5
90	10	1.30	2.30	11.9	2.10	82.40	1.59	6.44	396.1
85	15	1.50	3.00	12.4	2.12	80.98	1.64	7.00	392.6
80	20	1.60	3.20	12.9	2.15	80.15	1.67	7.25	391.55

Table 2: Sensory Quality of Acha – Beniseed Composite Biscuit

Sample Parameters		Colour	Texture	Appearance	Flavour	Taste	General Acceptability
Acha %	Beniseed %						
100	0	8.30a	7.20ab	8.50a	4.20ed	7.70a	7.90a
95	5	6.15b	6.85ba	7.55ba	4.95dc	7.65ba	7.75ba
90	10	5.40cb	6.45cab	6.85cba	5.85cb	6.55c	6.25c
85	15	4.55dbc	6.10dabc	6.30dbc	6.50b	4.65d	4.65d
80	20	4.30ecd	5.80eabc	6.30ebdcd	8.30a	3.70e	3.70ed

Score with the same subscript are not significantly different as 5% level of a acceptance

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